

Reactivity of Single-Atom Alloys as Easy as Counting to Ten

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Single-Atom Alloys (SAAs) have recently emerged as highly active and selective alloy catalysts. Unlike pure metals, SAAs escape the well-established conceptual framework developed nearly three decades ago for predicting catalytic performance. Here, based on high throughput density functional theory calculations, we reveal a 10-electron count rule for the binding of adsorbates on the dopant of SAA surfaces. A simple molecular orbital approach rationalises this rule and the nature of the adsorbate/dopant interaction. In addition, our intuitive model can accelerate the rational design of SAA catalysts. Indeed, we illustrate how the unique insights provided by the electron count rule help identify the most promising dopant for an industrially relevant hydrogenation reaction, thereby reducing the number of potential materials by more than one order of magnitude.

Single-Atom Alloys have recently emerged as a new class of catalysts able to reach high activity and selectivity for a range of chemical reactions (1–3). In these alloys, the active metal is dispersed as single atoms at the surface of a more inert host metal. This doping strategy significantly improves the catalytic performance of the otherwise poorly reactive, and yet highly selective, coinage metals (Cu, Ag and Au). There has been considerable work aiming at screening and predicting the unique reactivity and catalytic performance of SAAs (2, 4, 5). Despite the accuracy of the predictions based on density functional theory (DFT), a simple physical model describing general trends is still lacking due to the special electronic structure of SAAs (1, 2).

Traditionally, the catalytic activity of a material can be described using the binding energy of species involved in the mechanism of the catalysed reaction. According to the Sabatier principle, species should bind neither too weakly nor too strongly to ensure optimal catalytic activity (6), and the electronic properties of the catalyst determine the binding energies. For transition metal catalysts, the adsorption energy of a species linearly correlates with the energy centre of the electronic band consisting of the *d*-states of the metal (7, 8). This means that the more valence electrons the metal has, the lower the energy of the centre of the *d*-band and the weaker the bond to an adsorbate at the surface (Fig. S1). Although the *d*-band model has shown great success in understanding catalytic performance over a few decades, there are known limitations. For example, SAAs and the related class of near surface alloys (NSAs) can both escape the trends expected from the *d*-band model (9–12). Recent developments have shown that NSAs follow stability rules and require corrections to the *d*-band model to fully describe their properties (9, 13). But such an approach is not applicable to SAAs. Alternatively, the rise of machine learning has provided an efficient approach for the prediction of adsorption energies on traditional alloys and SAAs (5, 14–16). Albeit faster than and as accurate as DFT calculations, these models do not provide the fundamental physical principles that govern the stability of adsorbates on SAA surfaces. In a change of perspective, a few studies have suggested to consider SAAs as analogues of molecular systems (17–20). The stability of such systems is related to the filling of discrete states (atomic or molecular orbital) resulting in various electron-counting rules (octet, $4n+2$ aromaticity rule, *etc*) (21–23).

Here, we propose a change of paradigm in the way we rationalise the reactivity of SAAs. Moving away from the traditional linear scaling relationships that have limited applicability for SAAs, we demonstrate that a molecular orbital approach, albeit somewhat simplistic, provides profound insight into the metal/adsorbate binding mechanism. Screening a variety of catalytically relevant adsorbates on a large set of SAA surfaces, we show that the adsorbate/dopant interaction is strongest when the n_d valence electrons of the dopant (equivalently the dopant's group number in the periodic table) and the k valence electrons of the adsorbates interacting with the dopant sum up to ten: $n_d + k = 10$. This 10-electron count rule is supported by a detailed analysis of the electronic structure of adsorbates bound to SAAs surfaces and generalised to molecular adsorbates. Finally, we demonstrate that, without expensive DFT calculations or complex machine learning models, this rule can effectively help, experimentalists and theoreticians alike, to design SAA catalysts for targeted reactions of industrial significance, as demonstrated herein for the reduction of nitrogen.

Results and Discussion

Adsorption of adatoms

We start by analysing the periodic trends in the adsorption energies of key atomic adsorbates. Specifically, in Fig. 1 and Fig. S2, we show the adsorption energies computed with DFT for atoms (O, N, C and H) adsorbed on a whole range of transition metal dopants on SAA surfaces. Unlike the adsorption on pure transition metals (8, 24), we do not observe the monotonic weakening of the adsorbates' binding from left to right along the periodic table (Fig. S1a-b), despite similar trends of the centre of the d -states of the dopants (Fig. S3). Instead, we observe shallow W-shaped trends for adsorption energies on $3d$ metal dopants and deep V-shaped trends for adsorption energies on $4d$ and $5d$ dopants. Interestingly, the position of the minimum on $4d$ and $5d$ dopants depends on the adsorbate, but not the dopant's period nor the host material. When the number of valence electrons of the adsorbate decreases ($O > N > C > H$), the minimum shifts to dopants with more valence electrons (to the right of the period), as if the transition metal had to compensate for the smaller number of electrons brought by the adsorbate.

Figure 1. Periodic trends for the binding energies of atomic adsorbates (O, N, C, H) on Au-based SAA surfaces doped with (top row) $3d$ dopants, (bottom row) $4d$ and $5d$ dopants. The number of valence electrons is reported as a secondary x-axis, and the approximate position of the minimum is highlighted. The inserts show the unit cell used to compute the adsorption energy of the adsorbate in the atop position on the dopant. Results for the Cu and Ag hosts are shown in the supporting material.

To further analyse the interplay between the number of electrons brought by the adsorbate and those coming from the dopant, we can tentatively count the total number of valence electrons of the dopant/adsorbate system, ignoring the host metal. For the dopants, we consider the number of electrons of the s - and d -orbitals of the outer shell, which corresponds to the group number of the transition metal element. For adsorbates, we consider all the electrons of the $nsnp$ outer shell: these are the electrons that are traditionally considered when drawing Lewis structures. Now, if we add the valence electrons of the dopant and the adsorbate, we find that the minimum is associated with ten electrons for H and twelve electrons for p -block adsorbates (O, N and C). For $3d$ dopants, we can still recognise a preference towards binding to early transition metal for electron-rich adsorbates (O and N), and to later transition metals for adsorbates with fewer electrons (H and C). However, because of significant spin effects on magnetic $3d$ dopants, adsorption is weakened in the middle of the row, with a fixed extremum for Mn for all adsorbates. Indeed, if the effect of spin is unrealistically suppressed, $3d$

dopants behave like $4d$ and $5d$ dopants (Fig. S4). Interestingly, these binding features on SAA surfaces (shape of the trends, role of the number of valence electrons) are distinct from pure transition metal surfaces but analogous to the binding of ligands in organometallic complexes (as shown in Fig. S1), which are successfully modelled using a molecular orbital (MO) approach (23).

Figure 2. Molecular orbital model of the interaction of adsorbates on SAAs using hydrogen (a-d) and nitrogen (e-h) as examples. (a) Molecular orbital diagram for the dinuclear MH complex, M being an element of the d -block. (b-c) Crystal orbital Hamilton population (COHP) and projected density of states (pDOS) analyses for H adsorbed on (b) ZrAg and (c) RhAg SAAs. (d) Filling of the molecular orbital for MH. (e) Molecular orbital diagram for the dinuclear MN complex. (f-g) COHP and pDOS analyses for N adsorbed on (f) ZrAg and (g) RhAg SAAs. (h) Filling of the molecular orbitals. In the pDOSs, the contribution of the nonbinding n_δ and n_π states are highlighted in colour (blue and orange, respectively). The dashed lines in (b-c) and (f-g) shows the Fermi level, i.e., the energy cut-off between populated states (below the line) and nonpopulated states (above the line).

This analogy with organometallic complexes and the electronic structure of SAAs akin to gas phase atoms (17, 18) have motivated us to consider an MO approach to rationalise the binding of adsorbates on SAAs (Fig. 2). Based on the symmetry point group $C_{\infty, \nu}$ of the metal adsorbate pair, we can construct an MO diagram (Fig. S5). For H, the s -orbital can interact with the metal's d_{z^2} orbital, generating a bonding σ and an antibonding σ^* MO (Fig. 2a). The remaining four d -orbitals form the nonbonding n_δ and n_π MOs. We can therefore fill up to five MOs before populating the σ^* antibonding orbitals and thereby weakening the adsorbate/metal bond (Fig. 2a). Hence, for H, maximum stability is expected for ten electrons. Similarly, we can construct the MO diagram for C, N and O. These adsorbates have partially filled p -orbitals that can contribute to the bond. The linear combination of the metal d_{z^2} and the adsorbate's s and p_z orbitals generate a bonding σ , a nonbonding n_σ and an antibonding σ^* MO. Additionally, the linear combination of d_{xz} and d_{yz} with the p_x and p_y , form two bonding π and two antibonding π^* MOs. The two d_{xy} and $d_{x^2-y^2}$ dopant orbitals, which cannot interact with the adsorbate's orbitals, form the nonbonding n_δ MOs. For p -block adsorbates, we can fill up to six MOs, i.e., twelve electrons, before populating antibonding orbitals (Fig. 2e).

To confirm that our MO approach appropriately captures the binding mechanism of adsorbates on SAAs, we have further analysed the electronic structure of H (Fig. 2b-d) and N (Fig. 2f-h) adsorbed on Ag-based SAAs. When building MO diagrams, we are interested in knowing (i) where the MOs are on the energy scale (y -axis), and (ii) which atomic orbitals interact to form a particular MO (*i.e.*, atomic orbitals with nonzero overlap interaction). Because of the metallic structure of SAAs, this information must be extracted from the electronic bands of the system. This can be achieved using the electronic density of states, *i.e.*, the number of states found at a certain energy level, projected onto the d -states of the dopant (pDOS), and the Crystal Orbital Hamilton Population (COHP) that quantifies the overlap interaction between two orbitals (25, 26). Fig. 2b shows the COHP analysis between the d_{z^2} orbital of Zr and the s orbital of H as extracted from the electronic structure calculation of H adsorbed on ZrAg. The analysis shows a narrow positive peak at -2 eV for the pairwise interaction between the s and d_{z^2} orbitals: this is the expected bonding σ MO. The same plot shows antibonding σ^* states as a negative broad band. The four other d -orbitals, referred to as n_π and n_δ in the MO diagram (Fig. 2a), do not interact with any orbitals of hydrogen, and thus cannot be identified in the COHP analysis that only shows pairwise interactions. Instead, they appear in the plot showing the density of n_π and n_δ states (Fig. 2b, right) as partially populated, as expected from the MO diagram. When considering H adsorbed on RhAg (Fig. 2d), all the states are shifted to lower energies, with the σ , n_π and n_δ orbitals now being doubly occupied and the σ^* partially occupied. This results from Rh having more electrons than Zr. The same analysis for adsorption of N is shown in Fig. 2f-h. The COHP analysis shows that the sigma orbital indeed results from the interaction of the d_{z^2} orbital with the s and p_z orbitals of the adsorbate. About 7 eV higher up in energy are found the pi orbitals (blue curve). In the same energetic region, the COHP analysis shows that the d_{z^2} interacts again with the s and p_z orbitals of the dopant. This time, however, the binding contribution of the p_z/d_{z^2} interaction (pink curve) cancels out the antibonding contribution of the s/d_{z^2} interaction: this is the expected nonbonding n_σ MO. Overall, we can see good agreement between the proposed MO diagrams and the electronic structures as computed with DFT.

The common point between the MO diagram of H and p -block elements adsorbed on SAAs is that the optimal adsorption energy is reached when all the bonding and nonbonding MOs with d -contributions are filled (Fig. 2d and 2h). The only reason why we seem to have a different counting rule for H and p -block element, is because we are counting too many electrons in the case of p -block elements. The n_σ orbital, which can be interpreted as a lone pair located on the adsorbate outside the internuclear region, is consistently populated throughout the period and does not contribute to the binding or the saturation of the d -orbitals. If we ignore this lone pair, we end up with a universal 10-electron count rule for optimal binding of adsorbates on $4d$ and $5d$ dopants (Fig. 2d and 2h). It is essential to distinguish between the adsorbate's total number of valence electrons v and the number of valence electrons k that interact with the d -states, especially when considering larger adsorbates such as molecules (Table 1). For example, CO has $v=10$ valence electrons, but, as expected from organometallic chemistry, only $k=2$ electrons interact with a transition metal (23). With this distinction in mind, the dopants with optimal binding to a specific adsorbate is easily identified as those with $10-k$ valence electrons, later referred to as d^{10-k} dopants.

Table 1. Total number of valence electrons (v) and number of valence electrons interacting with the metal dopant (k) for atomic and molecular adsorbates.

	H	C	N	O	H ₂ O	NH ₃	CO	N ₂	linear NO	bent NO	C ₂ H ₄
v	1	4	5	6	8	8	10	10	11		12
k	1	2	3	4	2	2	2	2	3	1	2

Extension to molecular fragments, their geometry and reactivity

In the first part, we have shown the 10-electron count rule for the stability of atomic adsorbates on SAAs. We are now extending this rule to molecular adsorbates. For example, CO interacts with its lone pair located on the carbon atom (Fig. 3d). NO, as a radical, can either interact with one electron in a bent geometry or three electrons in a linear geometry (Fig. 3d). If we only consider the linear geometries, the 10-electron rule predicts the strongest adsorption energies at d^8 for CO and d^7 for NO on $4d$ and $5d$ dopants. This is confirmed by our DFT calculations (Fig. 3a). It is important to note however that this rule only holds when the binding trends between the adsorbate and the dopant are dominated by the sharing of electrons, *i.e.*, covalent contributions. H₂O and NH₃ are known examples of adsorbates for which the binding trends are dominated by electrostatic interactions (20). At the electronic level, this translates to a limited reshuffling of the electronic density of H₂O upon adsorption compared with NO (Fig. 3c). For these adsorbates, the DFT-computed

adsorption energies do not show the expected minima and roughly follow the steady variation of the electric charge of the dopant (Fig. 3b and Table S1) over the $4d$ period (from $-0.22e$ to $+1.61e$). It is only when we remove the electrostatic contribution, which varies linearly with respect to the atomic charge of the dopant, that we recover the expected trends for the covalent contribution with minima at d^8 for NH_3 and H_2O (Fig. S6). For these closed-shell molecules with highly polarised bonds (large electronegativity difference between O or N and H), the 10-electron count rule has less practical applicability and the atomic charge of the dopant is a much more robust descriptor of the binding.(20)

Figure 3. Adsorption of molecules and molecular fragments on SAA surfaces. (a) Adsorption energy of CO and NO on $4d$ -metal doped Ag surfaces. (b) Lewis structures of the CO, NO (including mesomerism), H_2O , and NH_3 on the SAA surface (black balls representing the dopant). The electrons highlighted in red interact with the dopant. (c) Adsorption energy of H_2O and NH_3 on SAA surfaces for which the atomic charges of the dopant are reported on the right y-axis. (d) Electronic density difference for NO (upper panel) and H_2O (lower panel) indicating charge depletion (yellow) and charge accumulation (cyan) upon adsorption on RhAg SAA (threshold of $\pm 0.06 e \cdot \text{\AA}^{-3}$).

Figure 4. Hydrogenation of nitrogen to diazenyl NNH. (a) Lewis structures and different binding modes of NNH. (b-d) Binding energy of N_2 and NNH (in different geometries) on Au-based SAAs considering (b) $3d$, (c) $4d$, and (d) $5d$ dopants. The shaded green area indicates the reaction energy, *i.e.*, the endothermicity of the hydrogenation of N_2 to NNH. By minimizing the shaded area, the reaction gets thermodynamically more favourable.

The significance of the 10-electron rule goes beyond understanding periodic trends in binding on SAAs: it helps identify active catalysts for targeted reactions. Let's consider the reduction of nitrogen to ammonia, a reaction of industrial relevance. On Au-based SAAs, the first elementary step of this reaction, namely the hydrogenation of N_2 to diazenyl NNH (see Fig. 4a), was identified as rate-determining because of its endothermicity (27). N_2 interacts with the dopant via its lone pair and is predicted by the 10-electron count rule to have an optimal adsorption for d^8 (Ru, Os) on $4d$ and $5d$ dopants (Fig. 4d). NNH, isolobal to NO, is according to the rule predicted to have an optimal adsorption for d^7 (Tc, Re) on $4d$ and $5d$ dopants. DFT calculations, shown in Fig. 4c-d, again confirm these predictions. Now, let's consider the trends in reaction energy required to go from the reactant (black curve) to the intermediate (green curve). Because of the rigidity of the periodic trends on $3d$ doped surfaces (W-shape with fixed maximum for Mn), the reaction energy of the elementary step does not significantly change when screening $3d$ dopants. However, for $4d$ and $5d$ dopants, the situation is different. Because of the curvatures and the different position of adsorption minima for N_2 and NNH, the gap between the two curves when the binding energy of NNH is the strongest. We therefore predict the first hydrogenation of N_2 to be most facile on d^7 dopants, *i.e.*, Re (and Tc). For reasons ranging

from stability, cost, to synthesizability, it is worth considering dopants around the d^7 minimum. Moving to the left of the periodic table (d^7 to d^6) provides viable options (Mo and W) with small thermodynamic barriers. Moving to the right (d^7 to d^8), however, is less interesting as the stability of the reactant N_2 reaches its optimum for d^8 , thereby detrimentally increasing the reaction energy.

Whilst this analysis is an early step towards the demonstration of a new catalyst for ammonia synthesis, it does however illustrate the power of our approach: it can identify the most promising potential catalytic sites and the extent to which we can extend the search for efficient catalysts to neighbouring dopants. Previous high-throughput and machine-learning studies (27, 28) had identified OsAu, RuAu and ReCu SAAs as promising catalysts for the reduction of N_2 , which are dopants close to the predicted optimum identified by use of the 10-electron rule. According to Dai *et al.*, Re dopants offer the best compromise between donation and back-donation to weaken the $N\equiv N$ bond (28). Our theoretical framework offers an alternative explanation. As we have seen, the binding mechanism of NNH to the dopant is significantly more influential than the properties of the $N\equiv N$ bond in N_2 . The stability of NNH controls the choice of the dopant regarding the most favourable reaction energetics, although donation and backdonation may, admittedly, play a role for the scission of the bond between the two nitrogen atoms in the subsequent steps of the reduction mechanism.

In the previous paragraph we have only focused on the linear geometry of diazenyl NNH, which is the most stable in the region of catalytic interest. We have identified two other geometries: the flat-lying and the bent geometries. The former binds to the dopant bringing five electrons and therefore helps early transition metals to satisfy the 10-electron rule. This geometry is indeed slightly more stable than the linear one for dopants with fewer than five valence electrons. The bent geometry, interacting with one electron, is the only geometry found for Pd and Pt dopants. It was also identified on Rh, albeit less stable than the linear geometry. For these late transition metals, the bent geometry, with fewer electrons interacting with the d -orbitals of the dopants, prevents too many antibonding states from being filled. The preference of early, mid, and late transition metals for the flat-lying, linear and bent geometries is again a manifestation of the 10-electron count rule (Fig. S7). Unlike atomic adsorbates, the geometry of molecular adsorbate can be modified to satisfy the 10-electron rule. Similar behaviour is well-known in molecular and organometallic chemistry and was theorised using orbital correlation diagrams (29, 30).

Conclusion

Although the surfaces of SAAs are metallic, the interaction of species at their surface can be rationalised in terms of an electron counting rule, like organometallic complexes. For $4d$ and $5d$ dopants, the strength of the adsorbate/dopant interaction is maximised for 10 interacting valence electrons. This corresponds to the saturation of the d -orbitals of the dopants. For an adsorbate that interacts with the dopant atom with k valence electrons, dopants with $10-k$ electrons will offer maximum binding. Previous studies have already highlighted the importance of electronic descriptors such as number of valence electrons, electronegativity, and adsorbates' frontier orbitals, for understanding or predicting adsorbate binding at SAA dopant sites (5, 14, 19, 27). Our work develops a unified approach based on the 10-electron rule, identifies, and shows the generality and predictive power of this rule. It provides a theoretical framework that identifies the key fundamental principles underpinning the stability of adsorbates on SAA surfaces. It also clearly identifies the limits of the simple 10-electron rule, namely when electrostatic interactions become dominant or when magnetic $3d$ dopants are considered. Finally, our model bridges the gap between the concepts of heterogeneous and homogeneous catalysis and, significantly so, establishes a clear conceptual guide, for theoreticians and experiments alike, for the design of more efficient catalysts, without the expensive or complex simulations only accessible to computational scientists.

Methods

All DFT calculations were performed using Vienna Ab Initio Simulation Package (VASP) version 5.4.4 (31, 32) with the projector-augmented wave (PAW) (33) method to model core ionic potentials. The nonlocal optB86b-vdW exchange-correlation functional (34, 35) was used for all electronic structure calculations except the systems with CO and NO adsorption. The plane wave cutoff was set to 400 eV, electronic convergence set to 10^{-6} eV and geometric convergence criterion was less than 0.02 eV/Å. The surfaces were modelled using a five-layer $p(3\times 3)$ slab, with the bottom two layers fixed at the positions of the bulk host. The pure fcc host metals were optimized in bulk and lattice constants of 3.60 Å for Cu-based SAAs, 4.09 Å for Ag-based SAAs, and 4.13 Å for Au-based SAAs were used. The slabs were separated by a 15 Å vacuum layer. For the screening of adsorption energies, a $3\times 3\times 1$ Monkhorst-Pack(36) k -point mesh was

chosen for Brillouin-zone integration, which was shown to yield the same trends as a fully converged $13 \times 13 \times 1$ Monkhorst-Pack k -point mesh (Fig. S6). All adsorbates were placed at the atop position and optimized using the quasi-Newton algorithm implemented in VASP, to prevent relaxation of some adsorbates to the fcc site. Overall trends are preserved for fcc-site adsorption (Fig. S7). The adsorption energies ΔE were calculated from the dipole corrected slabs with reference to gas phase atoms. Spin-unrestricted calculations were performed for all SAA slabs, but for better convergence the charge density of a spin-restricted calculation was calculated first and used as starting guess for the spin-unrestricted calculation. Adsorption energies of CO and NO were calculated with the RPBE functional (37).

Analysis of the electronic structure, *i.e.*, crystal orbital Hamilton population (COHP) analysis and projected density-of-states (DOS), was performed using Lobster (26, 38–41). Starting from a VASP calculation with a higher $13 \times 13 \times 1$ Monkhorst-Pack k -point mesh and symmetry switched off (ISYM=−1) the WAVECAR and other VASP output files were postprocessed using Lobster. Bader charges were determined using the VTST tools developed by Henkelman *et al.*(42).

The electronic population n_j of MO j can be determined summing over $pDOS_i$ of its contributing AOs i . For bonding MOs, the integration is performed up to E^\pm , the point where the COHP changes signs, *i.e.*, the point where the linear combination of AOs switches from being bonding to being antibonding (Eq. (i)), or up to the Fermi level E_F if $E_F < E^\pm$. For antibonding MOs, the integration is performed from E^\pm up to E_F (Eq. (ii)). If $E^\pm > E_F$, the antibonding MO is empty (null population). Similar integrations are performed for the nonbonding d and n_σ orbitals (Eq. (iii) and (iv)).

$$\text{Bonding population:} \quad n_{j(\text{bonding})} = \sum_i \int_{-\infty}^{\min(E_F, E_i^\pm)} pDOS_i(\epsilon) d\epsilon \quad (\text{i})$$

$$\text{Antibonding population:} \quad n_{j(\text{anti})} = \sum_i \int_{E_i^\pm}^{E_F} pDOS_i(\epsilon) d\epsilon \quad (\text{ii})$$

$$\text{Nonbonding } d\text{-orbitals:} \quad n_j = \sum_i \int_{-\infty}^{E_F} pDOS_i(\epsilon) d\epsilon \quad (\text{iii})$$

$$\text{Nonbonding } n_\sigma \text{ orbital:} \quad n_j = \sum_i \int_{-\infty}^{E_F} pDOS_i(\epsilon) d\epsilon - n_{j(\text{bonding})} - n_{j(\text{anti})} \quad (\text{iv})$$

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Author contributions

J.S. and R.R. performed DFT calculations. R.R. developed the MO diagrams. J.S. performed the DOS and COHP analysis. All authors analysed the computational data. All authors wrote, read and commented on the manuscript.

Additional information

Supplementary Information is available in the online version of the paper. Correspondence and requests for materials should be addressed to R.R.

Competing financial interests

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

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